

Durability of High strength concrete with self curing admixture and partial replacement of coarse aggregate with Bethamcherla stone waste under exposure of HCL Acid

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ABSTRACT

For traditional curing processes, a significant volume of water is needed. Working on concrete high-rise structures and in areas with limited water supplies makes this challenging. Concrete that doesn't need more water to cure. In this case polyvinyl alcohol, or self-curing concrete, will be utilized. Natural marble is the main component of Bethamcherla stone. It may be located in the Bethamcherla area of Andhra Pradesh Kurnool district. Bethamcherla stone waste is produced by the quarry's cutting and sizing operations and appears as overlying burden. Cement, water, fine and coarse aggregates make up concrete, a binding substance. This project will examine the effects of adding polyvinyl alcohol at different percentages (0%, 0.03%, 0.06%, 0.12%, 0.24% by weight of cement) and partially replacing coarse aggregate with Bethamcherla stone waste at different percentages (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50% by weight of coarse aggregate). One self-curing agent is polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and adding 10% of silica fume for more strength. The acid resistance of concrete in a HCL solution is the main topic of the experimental study. For the concrete specimens in a 5% HCL solution following a standard curing period of 28 days, this study takes into account the concrete grade M50 and curing times of 30, 60, and 90 days. In this experimental work will determine the mechanical properties of concrete such as compressive strength, split tensile strength.

Key points: Polyvinyl Alcohol, Bethamcherla Stone, HCL, Silica fume, Compression Test, Split Tensile Test.

I INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background : India's construction industry is rapidly growing due to urbanization, population increase, and large infrastructure development, leading to a rising demand for high-strength concrete (HSC) for buildings, bridges, and heavy structures. Although HSC like M50 grade provides superior strength and durability, its performance in aggressive environments, especially under hydrochloric acid (HCl) attack, remains a concern as acids leach calcium hydroxide and weaken hydration products. Conventional water curing is often ineffective on construction sites due to water scarcity and improper curing practices; therefore, self-curing admixtures are increasingly used to retain internal moisture, enhance hydration, and improve durability. At the same time, the depletion of natural aggregates from excessive quarrying has created environmental challenges, encouraging the use of sustainable alternatives such as industrial by-products and stone wastes. Bethamcherla stone waste (BSW), generated in large quantities in the Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh, can be processed into usable aggregates and effectively incorporated into concrete. Integrating self-curing admixtures with BSW in high-strength concrete and evaluating its durability under HCl exposure offers a sustainable

and practical approach to producing durable, resource-efficient concrete suitable for modern infrastructure.

1.2 Scope of the Project : The present study investigates the durability performance of M50 grade high-strength concrete prepared with partial replacement of natural coarse aggregates by Bethamcherla stone waste (BSW) and the use of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as a self-curing admixture.

The scope of this research is to

1. To develop self-curing concrete using polyvinyl Alcohol at varying percentages (0.03%, 0.06%, 0.12%, 0.24%) as an internal curing agent to reduce dependency on external water curing especially useful in water-scarce and high rise construction.
2. To utilize Bethamcherla stone waste as a partial replacement for natural coarse aggregates at varying percentages (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50%), thereby promoting sustainable use of quarry waste and reducing the consumption of natural aggregates.
3. To enhance the performance of M50 grade concrete by incorporating 10% silica fume as a supplementary cementitious material for improved strength, reduced porosity and better durability.
4. To assess the fresh properties by conducting slump cone test and mechanical properties such as compressive and split tensile strength at curing ages of 28, 30, 60 and 90 days.
5. To analyse the acid resistance of concrete specimens when exposed to 5% HCL solution after standard 28-day curing.
6. Durability assessment is limited to exposure under HCL attack, with observation at 30, 60 and 90 days.

1.3 Objectives of Research : The objectives of this study are to systematically examine the combined effects of Bethamcherla Stone Waste and Polyvinyl Alcohol on the performance of M50 grade high-strength concrete exposed to hydrochloric acid.

Objectives of this Research is to:

1. To analyse the combined performance of BSW + PVA in concrete exposed to HCL attack.
2. To determine the workability of all mixes under the slump cone test.
3. To determine the 28-day compressive strength to evaluate durability by testing compressive strength of specimens exposed to HCl acid of 30, 60 and 90 days.
4. To determine the 28-day split tensile strength to evaluate durability by testing split tensile strength of specimens exposed to HCl acid of 30, 60 and 90 days.
5. To identify the optimum combination of BSW percentage and PVA dosage that provides the best durability performance while maintaining adequate strength.

II REVIEW OF LITERATURE

G. Neeraj, Dr. Vaishali G. Ghorpade and Dr. H. Sudarsana Rao (2024) examined M50 concrete developed by partially replacing coarse aggregate with Bethamcherla waste stone and incorporating PVA as a self-curing agent along with silica fume. The study evaluated workability, compressive strength, and split tensile strength at 28 and 90 days to identify an optimal and sustainable high-performance mix.

Abdulaziz Alaskar et al. (2021) explored the use of natural lightweight aggregates (LWAs) for internal curing of high-performance concrete. Pre-wetted fine and coarse LWAs were found to significantly reduce autogenous and drying shrinkage, with fine LWAs providing more effective moisture distribution. The mixtures maintained adequate strength as per ACI limits, demonstrating that LWA-based internal curing effectively minimizes volume changes and cracking.

Ghantasala Nirupama & Jyothi Kumari Ganta (2024) investigated the feasibility of using Bethamcherla waste stone as a partial replacement for coarse aggregate, highlighting its potential to address natural aggregate scarcity and promote sustainable construction practices.

Dr. T. Suresh Babu et al. (2016) performed a comparative study on M20 self-curing concrete using PVA. The investigation measured compressive, flexural, and split tensile strengths under different curing conditions, demonstrating that PVA-based self-curing can achieve strength comparable to conventional curing, making it suitable for areas with limited water availability.

Prof. G. V. Joshi et al. (2019) evaluated the impact of chemical acid attacks on hardened concrete, noting that exposure to industrial and environmental acids significantly affects long-term strength and durability. The study stressed the need for proper material selection, adequate safety factors, and specialized admixtures for structures in acidic environments.

V. Kavin Kumar et al. (2021) reviewed the use of industrial by-products in lightweight concrete and concluded that materials such as fly ash, bottom ash, and rubber can improve mechanical and physical properties while enhancing sustainability when supported by proper mix design.

Badogiannis et al. (2021) evaluated structural lightweight concrete made with natural and artificial lightweight aggregates like pumice and perlite. The mixes exhibited higher porosity but improved chloride resistance, demonstrating their potential for durable and sustainable structural applications.

J. Alexandre Bogas & Augusto Gomes (2013) conducted an extensive study on SLWAC covering LC20/22 to LC60/66 strength classes. They analyzed compressive behavior, failure modes, and proposed a simplified method for strength estimation based on constituent properties.

Chetna M. Vyas et al. (2013) investigated the durability of concrete with recycled coarse aggregates (RCA) for M35–M45 grades. The study found that 40% RCA replacement provided the lowest water absorption and sorptivity; beyond this level, deterioration in durability properties was observed.

V. Jyothish Naidu et al. (2019) examined the replacement of natural granite aggregate with Bethamcherla marble stone aggregate (BMSA) and the addition of GI steel fibers. Increasing BMSA replacement reduced compressive strength, but incorporating 1–2% steel fibers improved strength across all replacement levels, demonstrating their effectiveness in enhancing BMSA concrete performance.

III EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

3.1 Materials and Composition

A. Cement : In this project, used the ordinary portland cement (opc) 53 grade in concrete mix. It meets all its physical and chemical requirements conforming to IS:12269-2013 such as specific gravity as 3.15, normal consistency as 32%, initial setting time as 40min, final setting time as 580 min, fineness of cement as 5%.

B. Fine aggregate : For the present study, well-graded fine aggregate passing through a 4.75 mm sieve was used. The sand was characterized by a specific gravity of 2.66, a fineness modulus of 3.01, and a bulk density of 16.25 KN/m³. Bulking of sand was observed to be 22%, and the material conformed to Zone-II grading as per standard classification.

C. Coarse aggregate : For the experimental work, Out of total quantity of coarse aggregate, 20mm (60%) which is passing through 20mm sieve and retained on 10mm sieve and 10mm(40%) which is passing through 10mm sieve and retained on 6.3mm sieve used. These natural stone aggregates procured from nearby sources were used as coarse aggregate. Their physical and mechanical characteristics were evaluated in the laboratory in accordance with IS 383:2016 and IS: 2386 (Part I),(part III), (part IV & V) –1963. The test results of 20mm aggregates showed a specific gravity of 2.68, water absorption of 1.2% and for 10mm aggregates showed a specific gravity of 2.70, water absorption of 0.1%. Combined aggregates properties showed as flakiness index of 19.20%, elongation index of 12.64%, impact value of 13.69% and abrasion value of 13.12% indicating satisfactory quality for concrete production.

D. Bethamcherla stone waste : Bethamcherla stone is a limestone widely used for flooring tiles, generating substantial waste during quarrying and processing. This stone waste poses environmental challenges but, due to its suitable physical and mechanical properties, can be effectively reused as aggregate in concrete, promoting sustainable construction and resource conservation. Bethamcherla stone aggregates were proportioned as 60% of 20 mm size, passing through the 20 mm sieve and retained on the 10 mm sieve, and 40% of 10 mm size, passing through the 10 mm sieve and retained on the 6.3 mm sieve. These Bethamcherla stone aggregates, obtained from local sources, were used as the partial replacement of coarse aggregate in the concrete mixes. The chemical and physical properties of the marble stone aggregate are presented in the following tables.

Fig 3.1 Bethamcherla stone waste 20mm

Fig 3.2 Bethamcherla stone waste 10mm

Table 3.1 Physical properties of BSW

Sl.no	Tests	Results	
		20mm	10mm
1	Specific gravity	2.65	2.67
2	Water absorption(%)	1.5	0.2

Table 3.2 Physical and Mechanical properties of BSW

Sl.no	Tests	Results
1	Flakiness Index (%)	20.16
2	Elongation Index (%)	27.03
3	Impact value (%)	23.1
4	Abrasion value (%)	16.28

Table 3.3 Chemical composition of BSW

Sl.no	Particulars	Results
1	Calcium Carbonate (CaCO ₃)	52.87%
2	Silica (SiO ₂)	9.8%
3	Calcium Oxide (CaO)	29.62%
4	Magnesium Oxide (MgO)	16.22%
5	Magnesium Dioxide (MgCO ₂)	33.92%
6	Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	1.38%
7	Ferric Oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	1.42%
8	Loss of ignition (LOI)	40.56%

E. Water : In the project using, JNTUA College campus tap water is used for both mixing and curing of concrete. The tap water is clean, potable, and free from harmful impurities, ensuring that it does not interfere with the hydration of cement or affect the strength and durability of concrete. Using tap water helps maintain consistency, reliability, and quality control of concrete specimens prepared for experimental studies and testing. It met the IS 456:2000 standards for casting concrete and curing specimens.

F.Silica fume : In this work, Silica fume is used as an 10% additional mineral admixture in concrete by weight of cement in modified concrete mix. Its fineness and chemical composition allow it to fill micro voids in the cement matrix, leading to denser concrete. It producing high-performance and durable concrete. Its properties as bulk density of 600 kg/m³, specific gravity of 2.3, specific surface area of 15,000 m²/kg.

G. Super plasticizer : In this project, FORSOC Conplast SP430 DIS was incorporated as a super plasticizer to satisfy the workability and strength requirements of the concrete mix. It enabled effective dispersion of cement particles, allowing a reduced water–cement ratio while maintaining uniformity. As per IS 9103:2019 it met standards. Its specific gravity is 1.18. Air entrainment is approx 1% additional air is entrained.

H. Polyvinyl alcohol : In project, using PVA as a self curing admixture in concrete mix. This admixture makes the concrete without external curing. Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) is a synthetic, water-

soluble polymer used as a self-curing admixture in concrete. It forms a thin film within capillary pores, reducing moisture loss, improved micro structure and promoting internal curing for sustained cement hydration. The use of PVA minimizes shrinkage and cracking while enhancing strength and durability, especially in high-strength concrete with low water–cement ratios. In this project 28 days curing is done by self curing admixture only without any external curing. The following table shows the properties of PVA .

Fig 3.3 Poly Vinyl Alcohol

Table 3.4 Properties of PVA

Sl.no	Properties	Details
1	Chemical Name	Poly-Vinyl-Alcohol
2	Chemical formula	$(C_2H_4O)_n$
3	Molecular structure	$[CH_2CH(OH)]_n$
4	Functional groups	Hydroxyl (-OH)
5	Polymerization	Vinyl acetate ($CH_3COOH=CH_2$) is polymerized and then hydrolyzed to form PVA.
6	Physical Appearance	White to cream-colored granular powder or beads also available in liquid form.
7	Solubility	Completely soluble in water.
8	Melting point	180-230°C (depending on the degree of polymerization and hydrolysis)
9	Density	1.19-1.31 g/cm ³
10	PH	5-7 (in a 4% aqueous solution)

3.2 Methodology and Concrete formation :

To achieve M50 grade concrete, the mix was proportioned with a water–cement ratio of 0.34 in accordance with IS 10262:2019. In this study, two concrete mixes are prepared for comparison Conventional concrete and modified concrete mix. Conventional concrete ingredients are cement (opc 53 grade), fine aggregate, coarse aggregate as 20mm (60%) and 10mm (40%) by total quantity of coarse aggregate, water, super plasticizer. For modified concrete mix, cement (opc 53 grade), fine aggregate, coarse aggregate as 20mm (60%) and 10mm (40%) by total quantity of coarse aggregate, Bethamcherla stone waste as 20mm (60%) and 10mm (40%) by total quantity of replacement coarse aggregate of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40% and 50%. water, super plasticizer, Silica fume was used as an additional supplementary cementitious material at 10% by weight of cement to enhance strength, Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) was introduced as a self-curing admixture in dosages of 0.03%, 0.06%, 0.12%, and 0.24% by weight of cement content.

For each mix 12 cubes and 12 cylinders were casted. In that cubes, 3 specimens are tested at 28 days under self curing and 9 specimens immersion in 5% diluted HCL acid. Later, each 3 specimens are tested at 30, 60 and 90 days. Similarly done for cylinders also. The experimental work aimed to identify the optimum combination of BSW and PVA that yields enhanced durability performance. Concrete formation is a systematic process that involves collection, proportioning, mixing, placing, compacting, finishing, curing and testing. The entire process aims to achieve a dense, durable, and workable concrete that meets design requirements.

A. Collection and Proportioning : All materials required for the concrete preparation were collected and weighed accurately. Weigh batching is followed and proportioning of materials was carried out based on the results of the mix design.

B.Mixing : Mixing was performed using a laboratory - type electrically operated pan mixer to ensure uniform blending of all materials. Mixing continued until a homogeneous and workable concrete was obtained. Proper care was taken to prevent segregation and ensure uniform distribution of materials throughout the batch. The mixing time varies between 1½ to 2½ minutes.

C. Placing, Compacting and Finishing : Place the concrete in moulds, Before placing moulds should be cleaned thoroughly, assembled tightly, and inner surfaces coated with a thin layer of oil to prevent leakage and adhesion. The concrete was filled in layers of approximately equal thickness, and each layer was compacted using a tamping rod of 16mm diameter of 25 strokes to eliminate air voids and ensure proper compaction. Steel trowel is used for finishing to make the surface uniform, smooth and achieve a accurate dimensions.

D. Curing : After demoulding, the specimens are stored in ambient laboratory conditions, allowing internal curing to take place naturally. This internal curing process was continued for 28 days, ensuring proper hydration and strength gain without external water supply. After the completion of the self-curing period, the cubes were subjected to durability tests under constant 5% hydrochloric acid (HCl) exposure to evaluate the resistance of the concrete against acid attack.

Fig 3.4 Self Curing

Fig 3.5 Cubes under HCL Acid attack

E. Testing methods : Tests on fresh and hardened concrete were conducted to evaluate the workability, strength, and durability characteristics of the mixes. Fresh concrete tests as slump cone test performed to determine the workability. Hardened concrete tests performed on cubes and cylinders to assess compressive strength and split tensile strength and its durability performance.

Slump cone : The slump cone test is conducted to determine the workability and consistency of fresh concrete, which reflects its ease of mixing, placing, and compaction. The test was performed in accordance with IS 1199 - (RA 2018) – Methods of Sampling and Analysis of Concrete. The standard slump cone used has a height of 300 mm, a bottom diameter of 200 mm, and a top diameter of 100 mm.

Compressive strength : Compressive strength is the mechanical property of concrete, representing its ability to resist axial loads. The test was carried out on cube specimens of size 150 mm × 150 mm × 150 mm using a Compression Testing Machine (CTM) of capacity 2000KN until failure.

Split tensile strength : Split tensile strength is a mechanical property of concrete that indicates its resistance to tensile stresses developed perpendicular to the applied load. The test was conducted on cylindrical specimens using a compression testing machine (CTM) of capacity 2000KN by applying load along the diameter of the specimen until failure occurred. Specimen diameter 150mm and height 300mm

IV TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS ON FRESH AND HARDENED CONCRETE

The results and discussions helps to understand the influence of Bethamcherla stone waste and Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA) on the overall behavior of M50 grade self-curing concrete.

4.1 Slump cone test : In this project, the concrete exhibited a true slump, indicating a medium level of workability varies between 50mm - 100mm. The test results and graph is shown below. Even though workability decreased, all slump values fall within the acceptable workability range for M50 concrete, ensuring that the mixes are suitable for handling, compaction, and placing operations.

Fig 4.1 Test results and graphs

The slump test results showed a decreasing trend for all mixes. These values fall within the medium-workability range suitable for high-strength concrete. It is showing a clear decreasing trend with higher levels of BSW and the presence of PVA. The reduction is attributed to (i) the rough and angular surface texture of Bethamcherla stone waste, which increases internal friction, and (ii) the self-curing action of PVA that binds part of the mixing water, reducing its availability for flow.

4.2 Compressive strength test : The following results shows the compressive strength of conventional mix on cube specimens before and after exposure of 5% HCL acid exposure.

Table 4.1 Compressive strength results of conventional mix before and after HCL acid exposure

Days	Strength in Mpa
28	63.6
30	61.911
60	57.689
90	56.311

The following results and graphs shows the compressive strength of all mixes on cube specimens before and after exposure of 5% HCL acid.

Fig 4.2 Compressive strength results of 28 days

Fig 4.3 Compressive strength results of 30 days under HCL acid exposure

Fig 4.4 Compressive strength results of 60 days under HCL acid exposure

Fig 4.5 Compressive strength results of 90 days under HCL acid exposure

From this test results and graph trend, observed that 0.12% PVA and 30% BSW has maximum compressive strength as compared to all mixes. In this trend graph upto 30% BSW and 0.12% PVA strength line is increasing after decreases. The conventional mix showed the compressive strength at 28, 30, 60 and 90 days as 63.6 MPa, 61.911 MPa, 57.689 MPa and 56.311 MPa which is slightly higher than the PVA–BSW mix as 61.87 MPa, 59.330 MPa, 56.356 MPa and 55.689 MPa. The modified mix is fully justified because it achieves nearly equivalent strength while providing superior durability, improved micro structural performance, and sustainable aggregate replacement through the combined action of 0.12% PVA and 30% BSW.

4.3 Split tensile strength test : The following results shows the split tensile strength of conventional mix on cylindrical specimens before and after exposure of 5% HCL acid.

Table 4.6 Split tensile strength results of conventional mix before and after HCL acid exposure

Days	Strength in Mpa
28	6.82
30	6.75
60	6.60
90	6.15

The following results and graphs shows the split tensile strength of all mixes on cylindrical specimens before and after exposure of 5% HCL acid.

Fig 4.6 Split tensile strength results of 28 days

Fig 4.7 Split tensile strength results of 30 days under HCL acid exposure

Fig 4.8 Split tensile strength results of 60 days under HCL acid exposure

Fig 4.9 Split tensile strength results of 90 days under HCL acid exposure

From this test results and graph trend, observed that 0.12% PVA and 30% BSW has maximum split tensile strength as compared to all mixes. In this trend graph upto 30% BSW and 0.12% PVA strength line is increasing after decreases. The conventional mix showed the split tensile strength at 28, 30, 60 and 90 days as 6.82 MPa, 6.75 MPa, 6.6 MPa and 6.15 MPa which is slightly higher than the PVA–BSW mix as 6.8 MPa, 6.7 MPa, 6.5 MPa and 6.1 MPa. The modified mix is fully justified because it achieves nearly equivalent strength while providing superior durability, improved micro structural performance, and sustainable aggregate replacement through the combined action of 0.12% PVA and 30% BSW.

4.4 Result Discussion : The compressive strength and split tensile strength results show a consistent increase up to 30% BSW for all PVA dosages due to improved particle packing and a denser aggregate structure. An optimum 0.12% PVA enhances internal curing and reduces micro-cracking, while silica fume further improves strength through micro-filling and pozzolanic action, leading to a denser ITZ. Beyond these limits, strength decreases due to increased porosity and workability issues. Hence, the mix with **30% BSW** and **0.12% PVA** is identified as the **optimum combination** with maximum compressive strength and split tensile strength.

V CONCLUSION

The experimental investigation on **“Durability of High strength concrete with self curing admixture and partial replacement of coarse aggregate with Bethamcherla stone waste under exposure of HCL Acid”** successfully achieved all the research objectives and established the performance characteristics of the modified concrete.

- ✓ All mixes exhibited moderate workability with slump values between 75 and 100 mm. This confirms that the inclusion of Bethamcherla Stone Waste (BSW) and PVA did not adversely affect fresh concrete behavior.

- ✓ Maximum compressive strength evaluation revealed that the mix containing 30% BSW with 0.12% PVA achieved the high strength among all modified mixes at 28, 30, 60 and days are 61.87 MPa, 59.330 MPa, 56.356 MPa, 55.689 MPa. The enhanced performance is mainly due to improved aggregate interlocking, reduced pore structure, and effective internal curing provided by PVA, which promotes better cement hydration.
- ✓ Maximum split tensile strength evaluation revealed that the mix containing 30% BSW with 0.12% PVA achieved the high strength among all modified mixes at 28, 30, 60 and days are 6.8 MPa, 6.7 MPa, 6.5 MPa and 6.1 MPa. The enhanced performance is mainly due to improved aggregate interlocking, reduced pore structure, and effective internal curing provided by PVA, which promotes better cement hydration.
- ✓ Overall, the study concludes that the optimum combination is 30% Bethamcherla stone waste and 0.12% Polyvinyl Alcohol, the resulting high-strength concrete exhibits enhanced durability, improved resistance to acid attack, and acceptable workability.

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